

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC PRAGMATICS OF MIMIC
IMAGES

Surayyo Mirzayeva Mahmasharif kizi
Shahrisabz davlat pedagogika instituti
mustaqil izlanuvchisi

E-mail: surayyomirzayeva92@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article explains the features of non-verbal or semi-verbal texts, collectively called “mimic images”. It also justifies the need for international relations specialists to master the skill of “interpreting non-verbal content” as an important component of basic language skills such as “semiotic approach” and “non-verbal communication”. It also proposes a general algorithm for interpreting mimic creative works and graphics.

Introduction. Communication is a multifaceted process of forming, maintaining and implementing interpersonal and intergroup relations, which arises from the need to organize and support human joint activity. Language is a complex, developing semiotic system, which is a unique and universal means of objectifying the content of individual consciousness and cultural traditions, ensuring its intersubjectivity, procedural disclosure in spatio-temporal forms and reflexive understanding.

The point of view of M.S. Andrianov is also interesting, in his opinion, “non-verbal communication is a set of non-verbal communicative means - a system of gestures, signs, codes used to transmit a message with high accuracy and playing a decisive role in semantic understanding of each other; in discursive psychology - the process of production and processing of paralinguistic speech” [1, p. 245].

It is worth noting once again that non-verbal means of information transmission are the subject of study of many disciplines. Doctor of Philological Sciences G.E. Kreidlin, relying on research in the fields of biology, ethology (the science of behavior), linguistics, logic, sociology, psychology, general semiotics, the theory of ethnos and ethnic systems, cultural anthropology, cogitology (the science of knowledge and cognition), and the theory of cognitive systems, identifies a whole discipline, non-verbal semiotics, “... its subject is non-verbal communication and, in a broader sense, non-verbal behavior and interaction of people...” [3, p. 6].

What is the specificity of a non-verbal or partially verbal fragment presented as a graphic or creative development? The author’s research in this area allowed us to formulate the following proposals. Graphic or creative development is a special type of text in which the content is presented in an abstract, structurally organized symbolic form through strong linguistic compression and reduction, as well as focusing on the most important. The content of the creative development is the quantitative and or organizational relationship between various facts, situations and phenomena of a political, social, economic, cultural, professional

and other nature, their state, relationships, interdependence, movement and development. Graphic or creative development, in contrast to the usual text, where the image, content is gradually revealed, allows for an instant visualization of the content.

The purpose of the mimetic text in the form of a real creative development is, firstly, to describe, clearly explain or generalize certain information, and secondly, to stimulate the interpretation of the abstract graphic or pictorial content and its connection with the general context of existing knowledge.

The specific features of a mimetic text as a creative development are determined by many factors, the most important of which are the set of basic information parameters and the nature of the organization of the content. The set of basic information parameters is expressed by graphic indicators, for example, thematic (subject of the image), temporal (relationship to a certain period), local (relationship with place and space), quantitative (units of measurement).

The main part. Mimic interpretation is the transformation of an image into speech, the verbalization of the non-verbal. The description is based on the type of mimic text. For example, a “state” image, reflecting facts and events over time, should present these facts and events in a comparative and/or hierarchical manner. A “development” image, showing the progress and development of facts and events over a certain period of time, should emphasize the growth, decrease, stagnation, and stabilization of facts and events over a certain period of time. The purpose of a “structure” that represents a certain structure is to describe this structure in the relative positions and relationships of its components.

Below we will consider the psycholinguistic pragmatics of a mimetic text that acquires a purposeful, expressive content.

The reference to the sacred spirits (“Ongod”) in the Mongolian Shaman is inspired by the seven shelves of a caravanserai and the passage through seven gates. Taking the form of calligraphic symbols that alternate between writing and painting, each gate represents an ancestral spirit and a storyteller. This contributes to a collective narrative intended to be a balm for the soul. Created in collaboration with weavers from Margilan, this work combines Mongolian and Central Asian button-making traditions, transforming fabrics into story-bearers. In the artist’s words: *“My work and world embody an endless journey through the invisible realms of being. Here, heartache is felt not only as a personal illness, but also as a general, ecological disruption of interconnectedness. Here, the wounds of the ground reflect the fragility of the human soul. “The teachings of the ancestors mean to me that in the human heart there is a desolation between heaven and earth, between the peak and the bottom of all things. “This devastation is felt in the deepest corners of our being and urges us to confront the delicate balance between all living things. I see it as an internal disintegration.”*

This work of art is a scroll-like, woven composition close to the aesthetics of calligraphy, created in collaboration with Nomin Zezegma (Mongolia, Germany) and Odiljon Okhunov, Javlonbek Mukhtorov (Margilan craftsmen). The continuity of the lines and the spiral structure in it express the ideas of energy circulation and spiritual connection of ancient Mongolian shamans. The rhythm of the weave represents the unity of “word - spirit - action” according to the principle of a continuous line in calligraphy. The form that forms the semantic (meaning) center of the work reflects the traditions of Mongolian shamans to communicate with the “angod” sacred spirits. In shamanistic ideas, “angod” was associated with the spirits of ancestors, protective forces and healing rituals. The continuous movement of the woven lines refers to the spiritual journey of shamans. The vibrating appearance of the lines is reminiscent of the shamans' ritual of "opening the way for the spirits."

The idea of passing through seven gates, inspired by the seven shelves of a caravanserai, refers to the multi-layered world in Mongolian-shamanistic mythology. "Seven gates" represent the process of the soul's journey through seven stages to a higher spiritual realm. These stages represent the shaman's testing of his spiritual strength, purification, and ability to establish contact with sacred spirits.

The end of a line in the work and the beginning of another line represent a state of discontinuity and destruction between heaven and earth, beginning and end, while the beginning of a new line reflects the philosophy of renewal and continuation. Thus, the work is not only a decorative-aesthetic object, but also a complex symbolic model that embodies the shamanistic spirit, the philosophy of unity and contradiction, accumulation and fragmentation, connection with the spirits of ancestors, and ritual ideas.

The text of the “Ongod” painting: *“Holy spirits that give strength to shamans. The wavy line is the spiritual path. The seven shelves are the stages of testing. The seven gates are the spiritual ascent from the bottom up. Calligraphic writing and calligraphy are the continuous*

movement of the soul. The oscillatory movement of the lines is the breath of existence, the duration of life. A break in the line is an internal breakdown, a break. A state of disintegration in the human soul, a state of disconnection from divinity for a certain period of time. The emergence of a new line is hope, a new path. The process of accumulation and restoration in the human soul. Reconnection to being. The end of the line is the last path, the final destination. The initial, middle and final destination of the body and soul. On this path, the soul passes from unity to contradiction, from wholeness to fragmentation. This state is not a loss, but rather a way to connect to a new path, to reach a new level of ascension."

Why can this text be considered mimetic? The text does not provide information about the creation and history of "Ongod". The text defines the meaning of "Ongod", its spiritual nourishment, and the state of the soul and body. "Ongod" is not a collection of wavy lines, but rather illuminates the stages of the ascension of the soul one by one. It explains the connection between being and soul.

Conclusion and discussion. The commentary, in terms of content, should be formulated as a didactic opinion or criticism, prediction or comparison. Opinion is a personal assessment, a personal attitude to the presented facts, their explanation and interpretation. Criticism is aimed at analyzing the presented content in order to determine its reliability and find errors. The prediction reflects the possible further development of the described material and identifies development trends. Comparison involves comparing and/or contrasting data with indicators from other sources.

In the practice of studying the nationality, history of foreign countries, the text has been, is and remains a very important tool for the development of effective and receptive speech activity. The text is defined as any piece of information that is perceived, accepted or exchanged between language users or learners, whether oral or written.

Analysis of a mimetic text in the form of a large number of diverse developments allows the author to distinguish the following main types of simple developments, based on the nature of the organization of their content: the "situation" image (depicts facts and events as a basis for hierarchical ordering and comparison), the "development" image (demonstrates quantitative changes in facts and events within the framework of "yesterday - today - tomorrow"), the "action" image (conveys spatial changes in facts and events within the framework of "from A to B", "from A to B and C"), the "structure" image (represents an organizational structure or a fact-event as a process).

The experience of professional communication in the field of international cooperation shows that the skill of working with a mimetic text (i.e., a person must have read and be an interpreter of this type of text) is very important, since it is an important component of the basic skills of international specialists, such as presentation and negotiation[6].

Conclusion. It should be noted that the skill of "interpreting non-verbal content" is currently gaining importance for a modern international relations specialist working in conditions of constant international and information communication.

Non-verbal communication is carried out through the language of signs and other elements of the human and surrounding world, which are similar to the letters and words of ordinary language [4, p. 4].

The features of non-verbal signs are encoded in the studied mimetic text. This speaks of the spiritual side of another people. From this we can conclude that the topic of this problem is relevant for the study of intercultural communication. Feelings that cannot be described in words are expressed in the language of non-verbal communication, since verbal expressions of feelings are often insufficient.

Thus, a brief analysis conducted to determine the features of nonverbal communication as a means of expressing nonverbal communication in mimetic texts allows us to highlight the following:

- nonverbal signs reveal the true attitude of people not only to each other, but also to everything around them;
- nonverbal communication arises spontaneously and manifests itself unconsciously;
- nonverbal communication channels of mimetic texts provide reliable information, since they are less controlled than verbal communication.

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